

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF A NOVEL ANTIFUNGAL EMULGEL FOR TOPICAL DRUG DELIVERY

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Abstract

Objective: The present study aimed to formulate and evaluate a stable and effective emulgel containing econazole nitrate for topical antifungal therapy.

Methods: UV-visible spectrophotometric analysis was carried out. A stock solution was prepared by dissolving 10 mg of econazole nitrate in 10 ml of methanol to obtain a concentration of 1000 µg/ml. From this stock, 0.2 ml was further diluted to 10 ml with methanol to obtain a 20 µg/ml solution, which was then used for spectral analysis.

Results: The drug sample was characterized as white, odourless, and crystalline in nature. Solubility studies showed that econazole nitrate was soluble in methanol, ethanol (95%), and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), while it was insoluble in water.

Conclusion: The developed econazole nitrate emulgel presents a promising approach for the treatment of superficial fungal infections by combining effective antifungal activity with a convenient, patient-friendly topical dosage form.

Keywords: Econazole nitrate, emulgel, antifungal.

Introduction

The development of an antifungal emulgels for topical drug delivery has received increasing attention due to their effectiveness in enhancing the delivery of poorly water-soluble drugs. Emulgels are biphasic formulations prepared by incorporating an oil-in-water (O/W) or water-in-oil (W/O) emulsion into a gel base. This system combines the drug solubilization properties of emulsions with the favorable characteristics of gels, resulting in improved stability, spreadability, and patient compliance [1,2]. Emulgels are extensively used for the topical delivery of antibiotics, anti-inflammatory, antifungal, and anti-acne agents. Compared with conventional dosage forms such as creams, ointments, and lotions, emulgels are non-greasy, easy to spread, aesthetically appealing, and capable of enhancing drug release, making them an effective and patient-friendly option for topical therapy [3,4].

Advantages of Emulgel

- Enhance the stability and performance of topical formulations.
- Facilitate the incorporation and delivery of hydrophobic drugs.
- Provide a simple, economical formulation with good spreadability and patient compliance

Method of Preparation of Emulgel

1. Prepare the oil and aqueous phases separately and formulate the emulsion (O/W or W/O).
2. Prepare the gel base using a suitable gelling agent.
3. Mix the emulsion with the gel base under continuous stirring or homogenization to obtain a homogeneous emulgel [5].

Fig.1: Formulation of Emulgel

Treatment of Fungal Infections with Econazole

Econazole nitrate is a broad-spectrum imidazole antifungal agent that exerts its action by inhibiting ergosterol synthesis, leading to disruption of the fungal cell membrane and inhibition of fungal growth. It is commonly used in the treatment of superficial fungal infections, including tinea versicolor, tinea pedis, and tinea cruris.

The present study focused on developing a topical econazole nitrate gel using a simple one-pot preparation method to enhance therapeutic effectiveness. Compared with conventional creams and ointments, the gel formulation offers superior spreadability, a non-greasy feel, improved patient compliance, and enhanced drug release. The formulation was prepared using an optimized Carbopol gel base containing propylene glycol and suitable preservatives [3,6].

Materials and Methods

FTIR analysis was performed to evaluate the compatibility between the drug and excipients. The melting point of the drug was determined to assess its purity. Solubility studies were conducted in various solvents, including methanol, ethanol, DMSO (dimethyl sulfoxide), and water[7].

Formulation of Emulgel

A 3² full factorial design was used to optimize the emulgel formulation by studying the effects of Carbopol 940 (X₁) and Span 80 (X₂) on viscosity and diffusion. Factor levels were selected from preliminary studies, and the experimental runs with coded levels are presented in the table 1.

Factorial design model for Emulgel**Table 1. Factorial design model for Emulgel**

Independent Variables			Level		
			Low	Medium	High
X1	Carbopol 940	%	2	3	4
X2	Span 80	%	1	2	3

Formulation of Econazole Nitrate Emulgel [8,9]**Table 2. Formulation of Econazole Nitrate Emulgel**

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Quantity in percentage (%)								
		F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
1.	Econazole nitrate	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2.	Carbopol 940	2	2	2	3	3	3	4	4	4
3.	Span 80	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
4.	Tween 80	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
5.	Propylene glycol	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
6.	Light liquid paraffin	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
7.	Cetosteryl alcohol	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
8.	Isopropyl myristate	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
9.	Methanol	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
10.	Water	q. s	q. s	q. s	q. s	q.s	q. s	q. s	q. s	q. s

Evaluation tests for Emulgel**Physical Evaluation**

The emulgel formulations were evaluated for colour, odour, and appearance. Colour and appearance were observed visually on a glass slide under good lighting, while odour was assessed by direct smell [10].

pH determination

The pH meter (Labman LMPH-10) was calibrated using buffer solutions of pH 4, 7, and 9. The pH of 0.5 g emulgel dissolved in 50 mL distilled water was then measured [11].

Viscosity

Viscosity was determined using a Brookfield viscometer (Amtech LVDVE) with spindle 64 at 10, 50, 60, and 100 rpm. Viscosity (cP) and torque (%) were recorded, with lower torque indicating better viscosity [12].

Spread ability test

500 mg of emulgel was placed between two glass slides and pressed using a 100 g weight. The excess formulation was removed, and the lower slide was fixed in position while a 20 g load was attached to the upper slide. The time required for the upper slide to slip was recorded [13].

$$S=ML/T$$

Where, S= Spreadability, M= Weight of upper side, L=Length moved on glass slide.

***In-vitro* diffusion Study**

Drug release from the emulgel was evaluated using a Franz diffusion cell assembly. The donor and receptor compartments were separated by a cellophane membrane pre-soaked in phosphate buffer (pH 5.8). The receptor compartment contained 25 mL of buffer maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and stirred at 50 rpm. Emulgel equivalent to 10 mg of drug was placed in the donor compartment. At predetermined intervals, 1 mL samples were withdrawn, replaced with fresh buffer, and analyzed by UV spectrophotometry at 220 nm after appropriate dilution [14,15].

Fig.2: Franz diffusion cell assembly

Antifungal Test

Step1: Media Preparation: Mueller Hinton Agar plates were prepared for the Kirby-Bauer method. For fastidious fungi such as *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*, the medium was supplemented with 5% sterile defibrinated blood. For fungal cultures, Mueller Hinton Agar (M173) was enriched with 2% glucose and $0.5 \mu\text{g/mL}$ methylene blue dye (GMB medium). The agar plates were sterilized and maintained at a depth of 4-5 mm[16,17].

Step 2: Inoculum Preparation: Fungal inoculum was prepared from five colonies (~1 mm) taken from a 24-hour-old culture grown on Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (M063) and incubated at $35 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ [18].

Step 3: Test Procedure: A sterile swab was used to inoculate the agar surface uniformly in three directions. The plate was allowed to dry for 5-15 minutes before applying discs aseptically. Plates were incubated at $35 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and examined after 20–24 hours for zones of inhibition, with rechecking at 48 hours if growth was insufficient[19].

Results and Discussion

Preformulation Study

Econazole nitrate was characterized as a white, odourless crystalline powder. The melting point was observed between 160-162°C, consistent with the reported standard, confirming its purity. Solubility testing showed that the drug is soluble in methanol, ethanol (95%), and DMSO, but insoluble in water [29].

UV-Visible Spectrophotometric Analysis

UV-Visible spectrophotometric analysis was performed using a Jasco V-550 spectrophotometer (Japan), and data were processed using Spectra Manager software. Methanol was used as the solvent system for blank as well as sample preparation. 20 µg/ml of Econazole nitrate was used and λ max was found as 220 nm [20].

Calibration Curve for Econazole Nitrate

The calibration curve of econazole nitrate was constructed by measuring the absorbance of different concentrations in methanol at 220 nm. It showed linearity over the range of 5-25 µg/mL in accordance with Beer-Lambert's law, with a correlation coefficient (R^2) of 0.9924, indicating good linearity [20].

FTIR of Econazole nitrate**IR frequencies of Econazole nitrate functional group****Table 3 : IR frequencies of Econazole nitrate functional group**

Functional group	Observed Frequency	Reported Frequency
N-H stretching (Amine group)	3447.76	3500-3400
C-H Stretching (Aliphatic Alkane)	3064.06	3100-2900
C=C stretching (Conjugated alkene)	1637.01	1650-1600
C-H bending (Methyl group)	1472.19	1465
C-N stretching (Aromatic amine)	1287.03	1342-1266
C-Cl stretching (Halo compound)	820.55	850-550

Drug-Excipients compatibility study

The FTIR spectra of econazole nitrate in pure form and its physical mixture showed no significant interaction between the drug, polymer, and excipients, indicating compatibility among them [21].

Evaluation of Formulation Batches**Physical Evaluation**

Some batches exhibited a smooth, grease-free appearance, while others were more viscous. No colour variation was observed among the batches, as all were white in colour, and all formulations were odourless.

Physical Characteristics of Formulated Batches

Table 4: Physical Characteristics of Formulated Batches

Batches	Colour	Odour	Appearance
F1	White	Characteristic	Smooth
F2	White	Characteristic	Smooth
F3	White	Characteristic	Smooth
F4	White	Characteristic	Smooth
F5	White	Characteristic	Smooth
F6	White	Characteristic	Viscous
F7	White	Characteristic	Smooth
F8	White	Characteristic	Viscous
F9	White	Characteristic	Viscous

Antifungal testing of Optimized batch

The percentage of Carbopol 940 and Span 80 in the formulation significantly influences drug diffusion. An increase in the concentration of Carbopol 940 leads to a decrease in drug diffusion, whereas an increase in Span 80 concentration results in enhanced diffusion. Among the two, Span 80 has a greater impact on diffusion, as indicated by its much lower p-value compared to Carbopol

Fig.3: Antifungal Plate

Summary of effect of independent variables on Dependent variables**Table 5: Effect of Independent variables on Viscosity and Diffusion rate**

Sr. No.	Independent Variables	Viscosity	Diffusion
1.	Carbopol 940	Carbopol 940 is directly proportional to Viscosity as it increases the viscosity also increases	Carbopol 940 is inversely proportional to diffusion rate
2.	Span 80	Span 80 is directly proportional to Viscosity as it increases the viscosity also increases	Span 80 is inversely proportional to diffusion rate

The antifungal study was carried out according to the standard procedure described in the experimental section. The optimized emulgel batch showed a zone of inhibition of 27 mm, while the standard antifungal agent (Nystatin) exhibited 28 mm. Based on these results, the optimized formulation demonstrated significant antifungal activity comparable to the standard drug.

Antifungal Zone of Inhibition

Nistatin is used as antifungal agent. Nistatin produces measurable zone of inhibition when tested against susceptible microorganism by using agar medium. The diameter is expressed in millimeters, which reflects the antifungal activity. A larger zone of inhibition means greater susceptibility of the microorganism to nistatin [22,23].

Table 6: Zone of Inhibition study of optimized batch

Sr. No.	Sample	Zone of inhibition (mm)
1.	Optimized batch (F4)	27 mm
2.	Standard agent for antifungal study	28 mm

Conclusion

Econazole nitrate emulgel represents an important advancement in the management of superficial fungal infections by combining the therapeutic effectiveness of antifungal agents with a patient-friendly dosage form. This study highlights that econazole nitrate, an imidazole antifungal, exerts its action by inhibiting ergosterol synthesis, thereby disrupting fungal cell membrane integrity and growth. The emulgel system, which integrates an emulsion within a gel base, improves drug penetration and enhances bioavailability while providing a non-greasy, cosmetically acceptable formulation. Overall, econazole nitrate emulgel serves as a promising option in antifungal therapy, offering both improved therapeutic performance and better patient compliance. This formulation contributes meaningfully to dermatological treatment strategies for fungal infections. Further research and clinical evaluation may help to establish its broader applications and optimize its use in dermatological practice.

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